

TEACHING METHODS USED IN THE PRESCHOOL EDUCATION SYSTEM.
ORGANIZATION OF EXERCISES.

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Abstract: The article describes the essence of organizing non-traditional classes based on a new approach to the preschool education system, the role and importance of using new technologies in teaching English to children of kindergarten age. The use of didactic games in the course of the lesson is based on its effect on the effective learning of subjects by children.

Key words: preschool education system, education, training, excursion, training, innovation.

Today, it is difficult to imagine the rapidly developing field of education without innovative pedagogical technologies. Pedagogical technologies have taken over every aspect of the educational field, including in preschool education, the organization of classes on the basis of pedagogical technologies gives effective results. Based on the requirements of our current development, educational standards are being improved, programs are being modernized and delivered to educational institutions. The material bases of educational institutions are rapidly being strengthened. Frontal (general), collective and individual forms of education are used in the preschool educational institution. In addition, children's education is carried out through excursions, didactic games, during the day in various activities of children outside of training, in the process of guiding their games. is the main form of giving. The training is the frontal informing of the children about the necessary knowledge and skills by the pedagogue. The educator provides education to children throughout the day: enriches their knowledge, develops various regional skills and abilities, such as cultural, hygienic, behavioral culture, speech, "accurate-accounting actions". But training is the main role in education. Classes are a form of organization of education in a preschool educational institution. The form of education means the specially organized activity of the teacher and the children and is held at a certain time in the agenda. The form of education differs depending on the number of children, the nature of the interaction between the pedagogue and the children, the venue, as well as their place in the agenda. knowledge and skills that ensure good mastery of the program material are acquired during training. In the classes, children are trained to think independently, develop skills, listen to educators, follow their opinion, distinguish the main ideas of the story from the stories being told, and develop skills such as brief summaries.

At the preschool age, the child acquires the highest peaks of perception of individual surface properties of objects, finds solutions to practical and mental tasks in a visual form. But the child is still indifferent to the appearance of objects. This is natural because objects exist for him and they interest the child only as an object of practical and intellectual activity. A child of preschool age works not on the essence of objects, but on their appearance and use. There is a big difference between how things look to us and what they are. The essence of things is not superficial, it does not arise behind personal experience, it is not directly perceived. It is discovered through socially organized learning - scientific understanding of the world.

The activities conducted with children of the first age consist of the interaction of an adult person with one child in a planned manner, and the purpose of these activities is to develop

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children's speech and movement; this is the stage of preparing children for activities; As the child's voluntary attention grows, such activities are carried out with several children. and then the whole group is taken along with the children. Teaching in classes requires mental and physical effort from children, that is, it is related to active activities, the child strives to achieve a certain result, which requires long-term voluntary attention from the child. Therefore, it is necessary to take into account the children's age and ability when preparing for the training: it is necessary to clearly determine the time of the training, its place in the agenda, correctly replacing different sections of the program. It is advisable to hold classes in the first half of the day, because the child can perform mental tasks better in the morning hours, and the room is well supplied with natural light.

The content of knowledge acquired by children should be educational. The program of the preschool educational institution envisages the acquisition of knowledge about nature in children of preschool age (which instills love for nature, nurtures the feeling of caring for plants and animals), content; children to the city of Jonahon on the basis of acquiring knowledge. to his homeland. love for people, love and respect for great people. interest in the country's social life appears. Preschool children have generalized ideas about social events and events. For example, the first ideas about the life of children in neighboring countries, the work of an ordinary person, the life and friendship of other peoples are formed. When the educator marks the content of new lessons, he thinks about how they are connected with the knowledge acquired in one or another lesson. For example, knowledge about the work of a cook, librarian and teacher is a part of the information system about different types of work. Knowledge about the work of different employees at the post office is part of the knowledge system about the collective nature of social work.

In order for children to be interested in the training and actively participate in it, its content and methodology should be well thought out. The more carefully the children master the educational activity, the more they listen to the teacher and easily move from the game to the training. Organizing children. The teacher collects the children and checks their readiness for training: looks, sits in the right place, tests their concentration. In order for the training to be successful, the children should be interested in the activities in front of them, and for this, they should use various methods suitable for the children's age, interests, and activities. The small group uses unexpected, riddle-based methods that are interesting to the children in order to arouse their interest in the activity. "Listen, someone is knocking on the door!" "This doll has come to visit us," you can start the training. This is how the activity that regulates children's imagination about things and what they are used for begins.

The educator tells the children in advance what kind of training will be held in large groups. This increases children's interest in the future activity. For example, he tells the children about going on an excursion to Independence Square a week in advance and tells them to look at the pictures and tell what they saw while walking with their parents. Children look forward to this day with great interest. It is necessary for children in senior and preparatory groups to understand the necessity and necessity of training, to consciously prepare for it. The main part. In the training, children are given new knowledge, they are guided and shown how to complete the task, and children in difficulty are helped. Team relations with children are carried out with a special attitude. In order for all children to be able to complete the task, the educator uses various methods and methods. It is necessary to be able to organize the attention of children from the

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beginning of the lesson. It depends on the mental task set before the children. It is shown and explained to the children what work needs to be done, so it is not necessary to repeat to some children separately, but all children should be taught to listen attentively, repeating only if necessary.

Children in kindergarten cannot read and write, so they cannot consolidate the material they have learned. Therefore, to strengthen the knowledge given to children, the teacher uses repetition and training methods. Mechanical repetition, memorization should be avoided, because material that is not understood is quickly forgotten.

If the exercise performed with didactic material in the process of consolidation includes an intellectual task, it will be of great importance in raising independence in children. For example, in a counting exercise, children perform exercises independently with the counting material: they reduce or increase the number of objects depending on the teacher's task. Toys can also be used for this. During the lesson, the pedagogue monitors the active participation of all children and their timely completion of the work. If the activity is carried out individually (drawing, making objects from clay and plasticine, building-making, construction), the teacher should finish the activity a few minutes before the end of the activity, because the children do the work at different times. warns them about

The teacher's demands on the children during the training should be appropriate to their age and capabilities. Children of the first small group will be trained in two. A nanny looks after the children of the second group while the educator conducts training with the children of the first group. During the training, the educator tries to actively participate all the children: to answer the question correctly, the equipment to be prepared, the preliminary work with the children (if necessary), the course of the training and the tools used by the educator methodological methods are shown. When describing the training process, it is necessary to highlight the organization of children at the beginning and at the end of the training (at the conclusion and transition to the next type of activity).

If the educator is going to conduct an excursion, he should go to the place of the excursion in advance, choose an object for observation, think about how to place the children, and choose the nearest and safest route. Small counting material, drawing training. application, construction materials. texts of poems and fairy tales are prepared in advance. Preparation for some classes begins much earlier. For example, in order to arouse interest in planting or transplanting a small group of children, it is necessary to show them a green plant. For this, it is necessary to grow it first.

So, didactic design in education in preschool educational institutions is a comprehensive comprehensive problem and it is necessary to study and put it into practice. Because the activities intended for young people should arouse interest in the process in children and be the basis for their healthy formation.

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